

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

DETERMINANTS OF BLOOD PRESSURE CONTROL AMONG HYPERTENSIVE PATIENTS ATTENDING THE FAMILY MEDICINE CLINIC, LAGOS STATE UNIVERSITY TEACHING HOSPITAL (LASUTH), LAGOS, NIGERIA

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Abstract

Background: Hypertension is one of the most prevalent non-communicable diseases and contributes largely to disability-adjusted life years (DALYs). It is a major cause of cardiovascular disease and premature death worldwide. Several factors have been reported to affect blood pressure control including age, gender, marital status, self-care practices among others. The study aimed to determine the determinants of blood pressure control among hypertensive patients in LASUTH to modify these factors to improve blood pressure control, reduce morbidity, mortality, and improve quality of life.

Methodology: A descriptive hospital-based cross-sectional study was conducted among 407 hypertensive patients. An interviewer-administered questionnaire was used to obtain relevant data.

Results: A total of 407 participants were enrolled in the study. The age range of the participants was 36-86 years. The modal age category of participants was between 61-70 years (39.6%) with a mean age of 65.25±10.7 years. Over three-quarters (76.4%) of the participants were females. About 60% of the respondents (56.8%) had good blood pressure control. The sociodemographic and clinical factors associated with blood pressure control were gender (p=0.045), employment status (p=0.048), number of antihypertensive drugs (p=0.031), and practice of home monitoring of blood pressure (p=0.007). The independent predictors of controlled blood pressure control were gender; (OR- 1.547, P-0.046; 95% CI: 1.034-2.484); employment status; (OR-2.028, P- 0.014; 95% CI: 1.140-3.608), the practice of home blood pressure monitoring; (OR-2.078, p-0.003; 95% CI: 1.277-3.380) and number of antihypertensive drugs; two drugs: (OR-1.886, p-0.026, 95% CI: 1.079-3.297) and one drug: (OR- 2.392 p-0.005; 95% CI:1.298-4.408).

Conclusion: Slightly over half (56.8%) of the participants had controlled blood pressure due to their female gender, unemployed status, practicing home blood pressure monitoring, and using one or two antihypertensive medications. The findings align with previous studies on factors influencing hypertension control. The reasons behind unemployed individuals having better pressure control are unclear and require further investigation. There is a need for primary care physicians to pay attention to these factors to achieve optimal BP control and invariably reduce morbidity and mortality among hypertensive patients.

Keywords: Hypertension, Blood pressure control, Determinants

Introduction

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), Hypertension has been declared a global and public health crisis.¹ It is one of the most prevalent non-communicable diseases and

contributes largely to disability-adjusted life years (DALYs).^{1,2} Annually, hypertension accounts for over 10 million deaths and 200 million disability-adjusted life years (DALYs).²

About 31.1% of the world's adult population live with hypertension, and 26.5% are in high-income countries while 31.5% are in low-and middle-income countries.³ Hypertension is more prevalent among African Americans with a prevalence of 43.0% in men and 45.7% in women, while prevalence among white men and women are 33.9% and 31.3%, respectively.⁴ The age-standardized prevalence of hypertension in sub-Saharan Africa is 25.9%.³ In 2017, the overall prevalence of Hypertension in Nigeria was 38.1% with a prevalence of 41.8% in women and 31.8% in men,⁵ however, the 2020 edition of guidelines for hypertension in Nigeria reported a prevalence of 20 to 40% in adults.⁶ In a recent meta-analysis, the pooled estimate of hypertension prevalence in Nigeria was 28.9% in both sexes, 29.5% and 25% in men and women respectively.⁶

Poorly controlled hypertension is a risk factor for cardiovascular disease, stroke, and kidney disease amongst others; hence it is of utmost importance to control hypertension which would in turn decrease the occurrence of these complications.^{7,8} Despite efforts to combat hypertension by pharmacotherapy, hypertension control rates remain low.¹

Several factors have been reported to affect blood pressure control such as age, gender, marital status, level of education, BMI, number of drugs, presence of comorbidities, adherence to hypertension self-care practices, practice of home monitoring of blood pressure among others.^{9,10,11,12}

The study aimed to determine the determinants of blood pressure control among hypertensive patients attending the Family Medicine Clinic at LASUTH.

Methods

Study Site

The study was conducted at the General Out Patient Clinic (GOPC) of the Department of Family Medicine, Lagos State University Teaching Hospital (LASUTH), Ikeja, Lagos, Nigeria. Lagos State is Nigeria's most populous state, with an estimated population of 12.7 million in 2019¹³ and 35 million by 2022.¹⁴

The Lagos State University Teaching Hospital (LASUTH) is located in Ikeja, the state capital. It serves as a training, research, and referral centre in the state.

Study Design

The study design was a hospital-based cross-sectional study.

Study Population

The study population included all hypertensive patients attending the Family Medicine clinic who had been on medication and followed up for 6 months and above.

Inclusion Criteria

All consenting patients aged ≥ 18 years who had been diagnosed with hypertension and had been attending Family Medicine Clinic for at least 6 months.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Any patient with hypertensive emergency.
2. Any patient too ill to participate in the study.
3. Pregnant women.

Sample Size Determination

Cochran formula for estimation of size in a cross-sectional study was used to calculate the sample size.¹⁵ A total of 407 participants were recruited into the study

Sampling Procedure

Systematic sampling was used to select participants into the study after calculating the sampling interval.

Study Instruments

A questionnaire containing three parts was used for data collection. The questionnaires was administered in English and interpreted into local language for respondents who did not understand English.

Part A: captured the sociodemographic data of the respondents including age, gender, marital status, religion, tribe, level of education, employment status and monthly income.

Part B: captured the duration of Hypertension, number of hypertension medications

Part C: assessed the Practice of Hypertension self-care using H-SCALE (Hypertension Self Care Activity Level Effects).¹⁶ This is a validated and reliable self-reporting instrument for hypertension self-care which assesses six self-care activities: Medication usage, low salt diet, physical activity, smoking, weight management and alcohol usage^{17,18} with a Cronbach's alpha of ($\alpha = 0.85$). The Cronbach's alpha of sub-domains; medication adherence, low salt, physical activity adherence, weight management, and alcohol use were 0.94, 0.74, 0.81, 0.93, and 0.92, respectively.¹⁹ A respondent who is adherent in at

least four domains out of the six domains of self-care practice is considered as having overall good adherence to hypertension self-care practice.²⁰

Part D: entailed anthropometric measurements which included weight in kilograms, height in meters and body mass index (BMI).

The blood pressure was measured using an OMRON M2 BASIC sphygmomanometer after 5 minutes of rest in the consulting room following the ISH guideline. The blood pressure at presentation was measured three times with 1 min between each reading; the average of the last 2 measurements was added to the readings of two previous clinic visits from the case note. The average of these three readings was used for the study. Blood pressure was classified as controlled (<140/90mmHg) and uncontrolled (\geq 140/90mmHg).²¹

Data Analysis

Data was entered and analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23; (IBM-SPSS, IBM Inc, Chicago, USA), a statistical software program.

The level of significance was set at $P \leq 0.05$.

Ethical Considerations

Approval was obtained from the Health and Research Ethics Committee of LASUTH with Ref. No. LREC/06/10/1619. The data obtained was treated with confidentiality. The identity of the participants was not linked in any way to the data collected. Those who had poor blood pressure control were further evaluated and counselled and their treatment was optimized. The purpose of the study was explained to each respondent. Written Informed consent was obtained from all respondents before administering the questionnaire.

Results

The age range of the participants was 36-86 years. The modal age category of participants was between 61-70 years (n=161 (39.6%)) with a mean age of 65.25 ± 10.7 years. Over three-quarters (n=311 (76.4%)) of the participants were females. Three hundred and nineteen (78.4%) participants were of Yoruba ethnicity. Table 1

The majority (n=267, 65.6%) of the participants had been hypertensive for 1 to 10 years. Figure 1. About two-fifths (40.3%) of the participants had a family history of hypertension and 74% of the participants had other co-morbidities with

diabetes accounting for 52.8%. About two-fifths of them (43.8%) were on 3-4 medications including medications for other co-morbid conditions. Half (n=206, 50.6%) of the participants were on two antihypertensive drugs. A larger proportion of the participants (n=315, 77.4%) practiced home blood pressure monitoring. Table 2

The range of SBP of respondents was 92.33-215.33mmHg while the mean SBP for the group was 139.69 ± 14.7 mmHg. The range of DBP for the respondents was 54.0- 124.33mmHg while the mean DBP was 81.93 ± 9.0 mmHg. A little over half of the respondents (n=231, 56.8%) had controlled systolic and diastolic blood pressure. Figure 2

On hypertension self-care practices, only 4(1%) of the participants were adherent to low salt diet. Almost half of them 183(45.0%) were adherent to physical activity, about half of them 215(52.8%) had good adherence to weight management and about three-quarters 291(71.5%) had good adherence to their medication usage. Almost all the participants had good adherence to alcohol abstinence 382(93.9%) and smoking abstinence 394(96.8%). Table 3

A little above half of the participants (n=222, 54.5%) had good overall adherence (i.e. adherence in at least four domains) to hypertension self-care practices. Figure 3

There was an association between blood pressure control, gender (P- 0.045), and employment status (P-0.048). Table 4 There was also an association between blood pressure control, number of antihypertensive drugs (p=0.031) and home blood pressure monitoring (p=0.007). Table 5

Participants who had good adherence to hypertension self-care had good blood pressure control however none was statistically significant. Table 6

Logistic regression analysis of independent predictors of blood pressure control showed that females were one and a half times more likely to have good blood pressure control compared with males (OR- 1.547, p-0.046; 95% CI: 1.034-2.484). Also, those who are unemployed are two times more likely to have controlled blood pressure (OR-2.028, p- 0.014; 95% CI: 1.140-3.608) compared to those who are self-employed or employed in the formal sector. Those who practiced home monitoring of blood pressure were two times more likely to have good blood pressure

control than those who did not; (OR-2.078, p-0.003; 95% CI: 1.277-3.380). Those who used two antihypertensive drugs were almost two times more likely to have controlled blood pressure (OR-1.886, p-0.026, 95% CI: 1.079-3.297) while

participants using one drug were two times more likely to have good blood pressure control (OR-2.392 p-0.005; 95% CI:1.298-4.408). Table 7.

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of participants

Variables	Frequency(N) (n=407)	Percentage (%)
Age group (Years)		
≤40	9	2.2
41-50	24	5.9
51-60	86	21.1
61-70	161	39.6
71-80	102	25.1
>80	25	6.1
Mean ± SD65.25±10.7		
Gender		
Male	96	23.6
Female	311	76.4
Marital status		
Single	1	0.3*
Married	252	61.9
Divorced	16	3.9
Widow	138	33.9
Religion		
Islam	95	23.3
Christianity	310	76.3
Traditional	2	0.4*
Ethnic group		
Yoruba	319	78.4
Igbo	57	14.0
Hausa	4	1.0*
Others	27	6.6
Education		
None	43	10.6
Primary	106	26.0
Secondary	117	28.7
Tertiary	141	34.7
Employment status		
Self/ Formal	181	44.4
Unemployed	76	18.7
Retired	150	36.9
Monthly income (Naira)		
≤50,000	258	63.4
51-100,000	90	22.1
101,000-150,000	24	5.9
>150,000	35	8.6

*Fischer's exact

Table 2: Clinical characteristics of participants

Variable	Frequency (N) (n=407)	Percentage (%)
Family history of hypertension		
Yes	164	40.3
No	188	46.2
Don't know	55	13.5
Presence of comorbid condition		
Yes	301	74.0
No	106	26.0
*Type of co-morbidity (n=301)		
Diabetes	159	52.8
Dyslipidaemia	60	19.9
Arthritis	35	11.6
BPH	24	8.0
PUD	13	4.3
Spondylosis	14	4.7
Osteoporosis	8	2.7
Others	19	6.0
Number of drugs presently using		
1-2	119	29.2
3-4	178	43.8
5-6	98	24.1
>6	12	2.9
Number of anti-hypertensive drugs		
One	130	31.9
Two	206	50.6
Three	58	14.3
Four and above	13	3.2
Practice home monitoring of blood pressure		
Yes	315	77.4
No	92	22.6
BMI class		
Underweight	7	1.7
Normal	99	24.3
Overweight	132	32.4
Obese	169	41.6

*Multiple responses

Table 3: Hypertension self-care practices among the study population using H-SCALE (n=407)

Self-care practice	Adherent N (%)	Non-adherent N (%)
Low-salt diet	4(1.0)	403(99.0)
Physical activity	183(45.0)	224(55.0)
Weight management	215(52.8)	192(47.2)
Medication Adherence	291(71.5)	116(28.5)
Alcohol Abstinence	382(93.9)	25(6.1)
Smoking Abstinence	394(96.8)	13(3.2)

Figure 1: Duration of hypertension

Figure 2: Pattern of blood pressure control

Overall self-care practices (n=407)

Figure 3: Overall adherence to hypertension self-care practices

Discussion

The mean age of the study participants was 65.25 years (65.25 ± 10.7). This is similar to what was observed in a cross-sectional study by Amoah et al. in Ghana with a mean age of 61.9 ± 0.6 years¹ and Menanga et al. in Cameroon with a mean age of 61.1 (SD ± 11) years.²² Conversely, a lower mean age was reported in similar studies by Okubadejo et al. (37.6 ± 13.1 years) in Lagos,²³ Abdisa et al. in Ethiopia (45 ± 12 years)¹⁹ and Desormais et al. (42.5 ± 16.5 years) in Benin, West Africa.²⁴ The variations observed in the studies could be because studies with lower mean age were community-based studies and others with higher mean ages which were hospital-based studies. In addition, more adults are likely to present to the hospital because of multi-morbidities compared to the younger age groups. The mean SBP in this study was 139.69 ± 14.7 mmHg (range 92.33- 215.33) and the mean DBP was 81.93 ± 9.0 (range 54.0- 124.33).

This finding is similar to what was obtained in a hospital-based cross sectional study by Omar et al. in Sudan with a mean (SD) systolic and diastolic blood pressure of 134.3 ± 15.8 mm Hg and 89.3 ± 46.3 mm Hg respectively.²⁵ Similarly, a randomized controlled trial by Hosseininasab et al. in Iran with reported a pre-intervention mean SBP of (144.4 ± 7.4 versus 145.9 ± 6.4 mm Hg) and DBP (85.5 ± 6.9 versus 85.1 ± 7.7 mm Hg) and post-

intervention mean SBP of 132.6 versus 133.4 mm Hg and DBP of 77.4 versus 77.2 mm Hg.²⁶ This is however lower than the report by Ogunmola et al. in a rural tertiary hospital in Ekiti, Nigeria that found a mean SBP of 161.0 ± 27.4 mmHg and DBP of 92.9 ± 15.3 mmHg.²⁷

This study observed that a little above half of the participants (56.8%) had controlled systolic and diastolic blood pressure. This is similar to what was obtained in a similar study by Ibrahim et al. in Southwest Nigeria where almost 57% of the participants had good blood pressure control.²⁸ This finding is however higher than the proportion found in similar studies by Ukoha-Kalu et al. in Southeast Nigeria where 50.6% had good blood pressure control,²⁸ Douglas et al. in South-South Nigeria (36.69%),²⁹ Daniel et al. in southwest Nigeria (4%),³⁰ and by Abdu et al. in Northwest Nigeria (27.6%).³¹ These variations might be due to methodological differences. For instance, the mean of two blood pressure readings at a single visit was used in some research.^{22,31} Another study used the mean of three blood pressure readings at a single visit¹¹ while some studies used a single visit blood pressure reading,^{32,29} however in this study; the average of three hospital visit readings were used to assess blood pressure control as done in the study by Qahtani et al.¹⁰

Table 4: Association between blood pressure control and socio-demographic characteristics

	Controlled (n=231) N (%)	Uncontrolled (n=176) N (%)	χ^2	p-value
Age group (Years)				
≤40	5(55.6)	4(44.4)	6.877	0.230
41-50	12(50.0)	12(50.0)		
51-60	47(54.7)	39(45.3)		
61-70	100(62.1)	61(37.9)		
71-80	58(56.9)	44(43.1)		
>80	9(36.0)	16(64.0)		
Gender				
Male	46(47.9)	50(52.1)	4.000	0.045*
Female	185(59.5)	126(40.5)		
Marital status				
Married	145(57.7)	107(42.5)	0.165	0.684
Unmarried	86(55.5)	69(44.5)		
Education				
None	20(46.5)	23(53.5)	4.471	0.215
Primary	65(61.3)	41(38.7)		
Secondary	61(52.1)	56(47.9)		
Tertiary	85(60.3)	56(39.7)		
Employment status				
Self/ Formal	94(51.9)	87(48.1)	5.929	0.048*
Unemployed	52(68.4)	24(31.6)		
Retired	85(56.7)	65(43.3)		
Average income (Naira)				
≤50,000	116(45.0)	142(55.0)		
51-100,000	47(52.2)	43(47.8)		
101,000-150,000	12(50.0)	12(50.0)		
>150,000	10(28.6)	25(50.0)		
Median average income	40.00 (20.0-100.0)	46.50 (22.5-100.0)		

*Significant; ** Mann Whitney U test

Table 5: Association between blood pressure control and clinical characteristics

	Controlled (n=231) N (%)	Uncontrolled (n=176) N (%)	χ^2	p-value
Family history of hypertension				
Yes	92(56.1)	72(43.9)	0.076	0.962
No	107(56.9)	81(43.1)		
Don't know	32(58.2)	23(41.8)		
Number of anti-hypertensive drug				
One	83(63.8)	47(36.2)	8.863	0.031*
Two	118(57.3)	88(42.7)		
Three	25(43.1)	33(56.9)		
Four and above	5(38.5)	8(61.5)		
Practice of home Bp monitoring				
Yes	190(60.3)	125(39.7)	7.199	0.007*
No	41(44.6)	51(55.4)		
BMI class				
Underweight	3(42.9)	4(57.1)	2.095	0.553 ⁺
Normal	54(54.5)	45(45.5)		
Overweight	81(61.4)	51(38.6)		
Obese	93(55.0)	76(45.0)		
BMI (kg/m ²)	29.75±7.4	29.45±6.6	-0.432**	0.666

*Significant; **Independent student t test; ⁺Fischer's exact

Table 6: Association between blood pressure control and self-care practice

	Controlled (n=231)	Uncontrolled (n=176)	χ^2	p-value
Adherence to medication				
Adherent	172(59.1)	119(40.9)	2.297	0.130
Non-Adherent	59(50.9)	57(49.1)		
Adherence to low-salt diet				
Adherent	3(75.0)	1(25.0)	0.548	0.459*
Non-Adherent	228(56.6)	175(43.4)		
Adherence to physical activity				
Adherent	104(56.8)	79(43.2)	0.001	0.978
Non-Adherent	127(56.7)	97(43.3)		
Alcohol abstinence				
Adherent	219(57.3)	163(52.7)	0.832	0.362
Non-Adherent	12(48.0)	13(52.0)		
Smoking abstinence				
Adherent	226(57.4)	168(42.6)	1.831	0.176
Non-Adherent	5(38.5)	8(61.5)		
Adherence to weight management				
Adherent	130(60.5)	85(39.5)	2.554	0.110
Non-Adherent	101(52.6)	91(47.4)		
Self-care practice				
Good	134(60.4)	88(39.6)	2.584	0.108
Poor	97(52.4)	88(47.6)		
*Fischer's exact				

Table 7: Multiple logistic regression showing independent predictors of controlled blood pressure

	Odd ratio	95% CI	p-value
Gender			
Male	1	0.886-2.324	0.142
Female	1.435		
Employment status			
Self/ Formal	1	1.128-3.620	0.018*
Unemployed	2.020		
Retired	1.249		
Practice home monitoring of blood pressure			
No	1	1.277-3.380	0.003*
Yes	2.078		
Number of anti-hypertensive drugs			
≥ 3	1	1.079-3.297	0.026*
2	1.886		
1	2.392		

In this study, there was an association between blood pressure control and gender with a higher proportion of females having higher BP control ($P=0.045$) compared to males. Gender was also found to be an independent predictor of blood pressure control where females were almost one and a half times more likely to have BP control compared with males (OR= 1.435, $P=0.142$; 95% CI: 0.886-2.324). This finding is similar to what was observed by Ojo et al. in western Nigeria (OR = 2.494, $p = 0.001$, CI = 1.477–4.214),³³ Desormais et al. in Southern Nigeria (OR=2.90, $p= 0.0296$; 95% CI:(1.11-5.57),²⁴ Okai et al. in Ghana(AOR = 3.55; 95% CI: 1.72-7.22),³⁴ Costa Filho et al. in a Brazil where women younger than 60 years of age had better blood pressure control (OR= 1.19, $p<0.001$; 95% CI:1.14–1.25),³² and other similar studies in which female gender was found as an independent predictor of good blood pressure control.^{33,35,34,36} On the contrary, Kim et al. in South Korea observed that the treatment outcomes for hypertension among young adults were better in married men than in married women.³⁷ This finding was related to the possibility that after marriage, men likely improve their adherence to medical treatment regimens and BP tracking with family support.³⁷ Gender differences in hypertension have been observed to be due to an interplay of multiple factors such as biological, behavioural, and attitudinal factors.³⁸ These findings are likely due to the fact that females are more likely to get treated and adhere to therapeutic plans than men.^{24,33} It has also been postulated that improved control among females could be the result of higher levels of awareness and treatment of hypertension among females than males.³⁴ In addition, females have been reported to have better health seeking behaviours compared to men who despite having poor health seeking behaviour also get involved in risky behaviours that can impact their blood pressure and overall health negatively such as alcohol intake and smoking.

In this study, an association was found between blood pressure control and employment status with those unemployed having better blood pressure control ($P=0.048$). This study found that those who were unemployed are two times more likely to have controlled BP compared to those that are self-employed or employed in the formal sector; (OR-2.020, $P= 0.018$; 95% CI: 1.128-

3.620). This finding is in the contrast with the report of a retrospective cohort study by Rumball-Smith et al. in thirteen European countries that found no relationship between not working and blood pressure control.³⁹ Similarly, Qu et al. in a community-based multicentre cross sectional study in China did not find a relationship between employment and blood pressure control.⁴⁰ On the other hand, Duncan et al. in South Africa found a relationship between being a full-time homemaker and blood pressure control however could not establish a relationship between unemployment and blood pressure control.¹¹ Kim et al. in South Korea also found that there was a relationship between employment status in women and blood pressure control.³⁷ The pattern observed in this study could be because those who are unemployed are not under much stress and are likely to rest well compared to those who are working and thus are likely to have better blood pressure control. However, there could be other factors outside hypertension that can explain previously reported associations, and effect modification could also have a role.

The practice of self-monitoring of blood pressure has been shown to have a positive impact on blood pressure control.⁴¹ In this study, practice of self-monitoring of blood pressure was associated with good blood pressure control ($p= 0.007$). In this study, home blood pressure monitoring was found to be an independent predictor of controlled blood pressure (OR-2.078, $p=0.003$; 95% CI: 1.277-3.380) where those who practiced home monitoring of blood pressure were two times more likely to have good blood pressure control compared to those who did not. This finding corroborates the findings in a systematic review by Sheppard et al. where self-monitoring of BP was associated with reduced odds of having uncontrolled clinic BP (OR 0.68, 95% CI 0.52-0.87).¹² A randomized clinical trial by Bryant et al. in the United Kingdom found that one year of SMBP with feedback to the patient or provider alone achieved 33.9% (28.3%–40.3%) blood pressure control.⁴² This finding is however in contrast with the study by Jeemon et al. in India where home blood pressure monitoring was not associated with blood pressure control.² A randomized controlled trial by Hosseininasab et al. in Iran also could not confirm that self-monitoring can improve BP control in patients.²⁶

The observed difference might be due to differences in methods of SMBP e.g. wrist self blood pressure monitor was used in the study by Hosseininasab et al. while other studies used the standard upper arm digital blood pressure machine. Most of the studies that reported an association were meta-analyses and randomized controlled trials. In addition, HMBP enables patients to be aware of their BP readings, hence empowering them to implement self-care practices in improving blood pressure control.

In this study, there was an association between blood pressure control and number of antihypertensive medication and ($p=0.031$). It was also observed that number of antihypertensive was an independent predictor of blood pressure control where participants who were on two antihypertensive drugs are almost two times more likely to have controlled blood pressure (OR- 1.886, $p=0.026$, 95% CI: 1.079-3.297) and those on one drug are two times more likely to have good blood pressure control (OR- 2.392 $p=0.005$; 95% CI: 1.298-4.408) compared with those on three or more antihypertensives. This is similar to what was observed by Amoah et al. in Ghana where the participants who were on one to two drugs had better blood pressure control ($p=0.001$).¹ In the same vein, Douglas et al. in South-South Nigeria found that patients who were on less than three drugs had better blood pressure control compared to those on three or more drugs ($p=0.03$; OR 1.65; 95% CI = 0.38-0.98).²⁹ Gebremichael et al. in Ethiopia also found that participants on less than three antihypertensive had better blood pressure control compared with those on more than two drugs, although this finding was not statistically significant ($p= 0.204$; OR 0.671; CI= 0.363–1.242).⁴³ This could be because the majority of patients on more than two antihypertensive drugs likely have uncontrolled blood pressure necessitating the increase in the number of drugs.

Limitations

1. White coat effect in measuring blood pressure was not totally excluded.
2. The study relied on data collected by questionnaire which might not be very accurate.
3. Some aged participants had recall bias about their self-care practices in the last one week.

4. There was no objective assessments the self-care practices such as measuring the amount and type of salt consumed or using a device such as pedometer to count number of steps under physical activity
5. The design of the study could only ascertain association not causality.

Conclusion

A fair proportion of the participants had good blood pressure control. The predictors of blood pressure control in the study were; gender, employment status, practice of home blood pressure monitoring, and number of antihypertensive drugs. There is a need for Primary Care Physicians to pay attention to these factors to achieve optimal BP control and invariably reduce morbidity and mortality among hypertensive patients

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Declarations

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Conflicts of Interest/Competing Interests

None

Code availability

Data and materials are available through the Correspondence author

Authors' Contributions

Sekinat Oloruntosin Odunaye-Badmus: Conceptualisation, Methodology, design, sample collection, write-up; Oluwajimi Olanrewaju Sodipo: Conceptualisation, Methodology and proof-reading; Sunday Olukayode Malomo: Conceptualisation, results, and proof-reading; Olamide Esther Oluwatuyi: Write-up and proof-reading; Ruth Nkiruka Odiana: Write-up and proof-reading

Ethics approval

Ethical was obtained from the Health and Research Ethics Committee of LASUTH with Ref. No. LREC/06/10/1619

Consent to participate

Consent was obtained using the LASUTH HREEC consent form prototype.

Consent for publication

Obtained from participants.

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